
Lex-Atlas: Covid-19 Dataset

Codebook

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Website: <https://lexatlas-c19.org/data/>

Version 1
from 24-01-2022

1 Introduction

The Lex-Atlas: Covid-19 (LAC19) Dataset is constructed from scholarly reports written to analyse national legal responses to Covid-19 in around 60 countries. The reports are the result of an ongoing collaboration of nearly 200 jurists as part of the LAC19 network and together form [The Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19](#). The reports cover a period beginning with the emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic in early-2020 and are updated to cover ongoing changes in different countries. The LAC19 network allows for a rapid and flexible analysis of the fast-evolving responses to the pandemic. Each report is structured identically with reference to a comprehensive [Author Guidance Code](#) so allowing for the accurate and comprehensive mining of the data outlined in this codebook. An additional benefit of our data is that links to the relevant parts of the country reports are provided alongside quantitative indicators, making the resource of particular use to a wider range of interested parties across both qualitative and quantitative disciplines. The LAC19 resource is made open-access on a permanent basis through the generous support of the Faculty of Laws, University College London, the Dickson Poon School of Law, King’s College London, and the Max Planck Institute of Comparative Public Law and International Law in Heidelberg, Germany. The LAC19 project is supported more widely by the UK’s Arts and Humanities Research Council and the Leverhulme Trust.

As the datasets seek to cover an ongoing pandemic, it is essential that the latest version of the data is used. We will publish both the latest versions and archived datasets at:

<https://lexatlas-c19.org/data/>

When using the Lex-Atlas: Covid-19 (LAC19) Dataset, please cite:

Jeff King, Octávio Ferraz, Andrew Jones and Roxane Agon (2022). The LAC19 Dataset. Lex-Atlas: Covid-19 Project. Version [...]. London: University College London/King’s College London.

When citing this document, refer to:

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2 Data Overview

We code reports compiled for the Lex-Atlas: Covid-19 (LAC19) project which examines the legal responses of a range of countries to the Covid-19 pandemic. The reports contain several sections, including the effect of Covid-19 on the basic constitutional structure, the legal framework applied to a country's response to the pandemic and the impact on institutions and oversight within a country. The data contained in each variable was hand coded by members of the LAC19 editorial committee who have a high-level of familiarity with the reports via the stringent editorial process.

Units	National and sub-national governments
Countries	38 A range of democracies and non-democracies spanning all continents
Time	Early-2020 to the present
Areas covered	System data Emergency powers Parliaments

3 Variables

3.1 Identification Variables

country	Name of country in English	
country id	ARG	Argentina
	AUT	Austria
	BEL	Belgium
	BWA	Botswana
	BRA	Brazil
	CAN	Canada
	CHL	Chile
	CHN	China
	COL	Colombia
	CRI	Costa Rica
	CUB	Cuba
	ETH	Ethiopia
	EUU	European Union
	FIN	Finland
	FRA	France
	DEU	Germany
	GHA	Ghana
	HKG	Hong Kong
	HUN	Hungary
	IND	India
	IDN	Indonesia
	IRN	Iran
	IRL	Ireland
	ISR	Israel
	ITA	Italy
	JAM	Jamaica
	JPN	Japan
	KAZ	Kazakhstan
	KEN	Kenya
	KOR	Korea, Republic of
	LVA	Latvia
	LBN	Lebanon
	MYS	Malaysia
	MEX	Mexico
	NLD	Netherlands
	NZL	New Zealand
	NGA	Nigeria
	NOR	Norway
	PAK	Pakistan
	PER	Peru
	PHL	Philippines, The
	POL	Poland
	PRT	Portugal

ROU	Romania
RUS	Russia
SRB	Serbia
SGP	Singapore
ZAF	South Africa
ESP	Spain
LKA	Sri Lanka
SWE	Sweden
CHE	Switzerland
TWN	Taiwan
THA	Thailand
TUN	Tunisia
TUR	Turkey
GBR	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
VEN	Venezuela

date (law as
it stood on)

Most recent date that the law in the dataset was updated for each country.

continent

Africa
Asia
Europe
North America
Oceania
South America

3.2 System & Government Type Variables

system_type	Communist Monarchy Parliamentary Presidential Semi-presidential Transitional
system_struct	Federal Unitary
government_type (as of 11 March 2020)	<u>Parliamentary system</u> single-party coalition <u>Presidential/semi-presidential system*¹</u> divided unified
parliamentary_basis (as of 11 March 2020)	majority minority NA - Presidential systems
pandemic_election	Has a national/federal-level election been held in the country since 11 March 2020? Yes No
system/government_notes	String variable including any additional information on the system or government type, including notes on changes resulting from elections held since 11 March 2020.
pandemic_election_date	Date variable indicating the day the election since 11 March 2020 was held. (format - dd/mm/yyyy)
post-election_gov_type	<u>Parliamentary system</u> single-party coalition <u>Presidential/semi-presidential system</u>

¹A divided government type is where the party of the President does not hold a majority of seats in the legislature and is not represented in the parliamentary cabinet. A unified government type is where the President's party does hold a majority of seats and/or is represented in the parliamentary cabinet.

	divided unified
post-election parl basis	majority minority NA - Presidential systems
government change	Did the election held after 11 March 2020 result in a change of government type or change in the majority or minority basis of the government? Yes No
government change	Did the election held after 11 March 2020 result in a change in the parties that are in government? Yes No

3.3 Emergency Powers Variables

Declaration of emergency	<p>Has there been declaration of emergency announced at the national/federal level in response to the Covid-19 pandemic?</p> <p>Yes/No, plus description</p>
Hyperlink	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the declaration of emergency is discussed.</p>
Coding	<p>Binary variable indicating whether a state of emergency was declared in the country in response to Covid-19.</p> <p>0 - No 1 - Yes</p>
Constitutional	<p>Has there been a constitutional state of emergency called in the country?</p> <p>Yes/No, plus description NA - no emergency declaration called</p>
Hyperlink2	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the constitutional state of emergency is discussed.</p>
Coding2	<p>Binary variable indicating whether a constitutional state of emergency was declared in the country in response to Covid-19.</p> <p>0 - No 1 - Yes</p>
Statutory	<p>Has there been a statutory state of emergency, or analogous measure, declared?</p> <p>Yes/No, plus description NA - no emergency declaration called</p>

Hyperlink3	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the statutory state of emergency is discussed.
Coding3	Binary variable indicating whether a statutory state of emergency was declared in the country in response to Covid-19. 0 - No 1 - Yes
Suspension of bill of rights	Has there been a suspensions of the bill of rights? Yes/No, plus description
Hyperlink4	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the suspension of the bill of rights is discussed.
Coding4	Binary variable indicating whether there has been a suspension of the bill of rights in the country in response to Covid-19. 0 - No 1 - Yes
Suspension/postponement of elections	String variable detailing suspensions or postponements of elections in the country as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic.
Hyperlink5	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the suspended/postponed elections are discussed.
Coding5	Categorical variable indicating the level at which elections were suspended or postponed in response to Covid-19. 0 - None 1 - Postponement of local elections 2 - Postponement of state/provincial elections

	<p>3 - Postponement of national/federal elections 4 - Postponement of referendum</p>
Stay-at-home orders	<p>Has there been a stay-at-home order in the country as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic?</p> <p>Yes/No, plus description</p>
Hyperlink6	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the stay-at-home order is discussed.</p>
Coding6	<p>Binary variable indicating whether there has been a stay-at-home order in the country in response to Covid-19.</p> <p>0 - No 1 - Yes</p>
Sunset provisions on stay-at-home orders	<p>Was a sunset provision attached to the stay-at-home order?</p> <p>Yes/No, plus description NA - No stay-at-home order or sunset provision not mentioned</p>
Hyperlink7	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the sunset provision of the stay-at-home order is discussed.</p>
Stay-at-home orders proper (timewise)?	<p>Is the decision to impose stay-at-home orders proper (timewise)?</p> <p>Yes/No, if 'yes' then dates included NA - No stay-at-home order or sunset provision not mentioned</p>
Hyperlink8	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the proper status of the stay-at-home order is discussed.</p>

Parliament continued to meet?	String variable detailing the interruption of Parliament resulting from Covid-19.
Hyperlink9	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the continued meeting of parliament is discussed.
Did Parliament continue to meet?	Binary variable indicating whether parliament continued to meet during the Covid-19 pandemic. 0 - No 1 - Yes
Rule-making powers dependent on emergency?	Was rule-making power dependent on an emergency declaration during the pandemic? Yes/No, plus description
Hyperlink10	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where rule-making power is discussed.
Coding10	Binary variable indicating whether rule-making power was dependent on an emergency declaration during the pandemic. 0 - No 1 - Yes
Ex ante judicial review	Was rule-making power subjected to ex ante judicial review? Yes/No, plus description
Hyperlink11	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where ex-ante judicial review of rule-making powers is discussed.

Coding11	<p>Binary variable indicating whether rule-making power was subjected to ex ante judicial review.</p> <p>0 - No 1 - Yes</p>
Type of parliamentary scrutiny (general)	<p>String variable detailing the type of parliamentary scrutiny in general (e.g. ex ante, ex post, no scrutiny).</p>
Hyperlink12	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where general parliamentary scrutiny is discussed.</p>
Type of parliamentary scrutiny (per instrument)	<p>String variable detailing the type of parliamentary scrutiny per instrument.</p>
Hyperlink13	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the parliamentary scrutiny of instruments is discussed.</p>
Coding13	<p>Category of parliamentary scrutiny per instrument.</p> <p>0 - no scrutiny 1 - negative 2 - made affirmative 3 - draft affirmative 4 - a mix</p>
Amendment possible?	<p>String variable detailing the possibility of amending the declaration of emergency/statute/individual regulations.</p>
Hyperlink14	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the possibility of amending the declaration of emergency/statute/individual regulations is discussed.</p>

Approval by 'package'	Were public health measures approved by Parliament in a 'package' containing more than one measure?
Hyperlink15	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where parliamentary approval of public health measures is discussed.
Were fast-track procedures used, and if so, what for?	String variable detailing fast-track procedures and what they were used for.
Hyperlink16	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where fast-track procedures and their uses is discussed.
Existence of coalition committees	Is there coalition parliamentary committees present in the system? Yes/No, plus description
Hyperlink17	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the use of coalition committees is discussed.
Ex post judicial review	Was rule-making power subjected to ex post judicial review? Yes/No, plus description
Hyperlink18	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where ex-post judicial review of rule-making powers is discussed.
Coding18	Binary variable indicating whether rule-making power was subjected to ex-post judicial review. 0 - No 1 - Yes

What type of statute for emergency powers?	<p>What type of statute was there for emergency powers?</p> <p>1 - pre-existing statutes 2 - Covid-19 responsive statute 3 - combination of the two</p>
Hyperlink19	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the type of statute used for emergency powers is discussed.</p>
General - sunset provisions	<p>String variable indicating the use of sunset provisions generally.</p>
Hyperlink20	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the use of general sunset provisions is discussed.</p>
Coding20	<p>Binary variable indicating whether a general sunset provision was used.</p> <p>0 - No 1 - Yes</p>
Sunset provision - emergency declaration	<p>Did the emergency declaration contain a sunset provision?</p> <p>Yes/No, plus description NA - no declaration of emergency</p>
Sunset provision - statute	<p>Did the statutory response to the pandemic contain a sunset provision?</p> <p>Yes/No, plus description NA - no applicable statute</p>
Sunset provision - individual regulations	<p>Did the individual regulations responding to the pandemic contain a sunset provision?</p>

	<p>Yes/No, plus description NA - no applicable statute</p>
Hyperlink21	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the use of general sunset provisions for individual regulations is discussed.</p>
Coding21	<p>Binary variable indicating whether sunset provision were attached to individual regulations.</p> <p>0 - No 1 - Yes</p>
Renewal - emergency declaration	<p>Can the declaration of emergency be renewed?</p> <p>Yes/No, plus description NA - no declaration of emergency</p>
Renewal - statute	<p>Can the statute used to respond to the pandemic be renewed?</p> <p>Yes/No, plus description NA - no applicable statute</p>
Renewal - individual regulations	<p>Can the individual regulations used to respond to the pandemic be renewed?</p> <p>Yes/No, plus description NA - no applicable statute</p>
Hyperlink22	<p>If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the renewal of individual regulations is discussed.</p>
Derogation	<p>Did the country derogate from international law in its response to the Covid-19 pandemic?</p> <p>Yes/No, plus description NA - no applicable statute</p>

Hyperlink23	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where the derogation from international law is discussed.
Coding23	<p>Did the country derogate from international law in its response to the Covid-19 pandemic?</p> <p>0 - No 1 - Yes</p>
Opposition from opposition parties	String variable detailing opposition from opposition parties to the government’s response to Covid-19?
Hyperlink24	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where opposition from opposition parties is discussed.
Coding24	<p>Category of opposition from parties to the government’s response to Covid-19?</p> <p>0 - No opposition 1 - Some criticism but no challenge 2 - Strong opposition and eventual challenges</p>
Constitutional changes	String variable indicating whether the response to the pandemic change the basic constitutional arrangements.
Hyperlink25	If applicable, a link to the the part of the national report in the Oxford Compendium of National Legal Responses to Covid-19 where changes to the constitution resulting from the response to the pandemic is discussed.
Coding25	<p>Did the response to the pandemic change the basic constitutional arrangements?</p> <p>0 - No</p>

Miscellaneous

1 - Yes

String variable containing any other relevant information regarding emergency powers.

3.4 Parliament Variables

All variables in the Parliament dataset refer to national/federal-level Parliaments.

Parliament suspended/postponed	<p>Has Parliament been suspended or postponed in response to Covid-19?</p> <p>Yes No</p>
Parliament closure notes	<p>String variable including any relevant information on the closure of Parliament.</p>
date closed	<p>Date variable indicating the first day Parliament was closed due to Covid-19. (format - dd/mm/yyyy)</p>
date reopened	<p>Date variable indicating the day Parliament reopened after closure. (format - dd/mm/yyyy)</p>
Parliament reduced	<p>Has the operation of Parliament been reduced in any way in response to Covid-19?</p> <p>Yes No</p>
Parliament reduction notes	<p>String variable including any relevant information on the reduction of parliamentary operations.</p>
Parliamentary debate reduced	<p>Has access to Parliamentary debate been reduced, either in terms of the physical presence of members or a reduction of normal operations, as a response to Covid-19?</p> <p>Yes No</p>
Committees reduced	<p>Have committee proceedings been reduced, either in terms of the physical presence of members or a reduction of normal operations, as a response to Covid-19?</p> <p>Yes No</p>

Virtual/hybrid in chamber	<p>Were debate proceedings conducted in either a virtual or hybrid format during the pandemic?</p> <p>Yes No</p>
Virtual/hybrid in committee	<p>Were committee proceedings conducted in either a virtual or hybrid format during the pandemic?</p> <p>Yes No</p>
Virtual/hybrid notes	<p>String variable including any relevant information on the use of virtual or hybrid proceedings in Parliament.</p>
Alternative voting	<p>Were alternative methods of voting adopted in either the chamber or in committees during the pandemic?</p> <p>Yes No</p>
Alternative voting notes	<p>String variable including any relevant information on the use of alternative methods of voting in Parliament.</p>
Oversight committee: specific	<p>Was a committee formed just for oversight of Covid-19 measures?</p> <p>Yes No</p>
Oversight committee: existing	<p>Was an existing committee, or committees, used to scrutinise Covid-19 legislation?</p> <p>Yes No</p>
Committee oversight notes	<p>String variable including any relevant information on the use of new or existing committees for oversight of Covid-19 measures.</p>
Committee chaired by opposition	<p>Was the committee, or committees, used to scrutinise Covid-19 legislation, chaired by a member of an</p>

opposition party?

Yes

No

Parliamentary oversight notes

String variable including any relevant information on parliamentary oversight during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Consensus over response

Was general consensus reached over the response to Covid-19 in the country?

Yes

No

Consensus notes

String variable detailing agreements and/or disagreements, either inside or outside of Parliament, over the country's response to Covid-19.